

PHYSICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS INFLUENCING MATERNAL NON-COMPLIANCE WITH IMMUNIZATION SCHEDULE

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the physical and psychological variables influencing maternal non-compliance with immunization schedules of children 0-2 years. The descriptive survey research design was used for the study. A questionnaire tagged "Maternal Non-compliance with Immunization Schedule Questionnaire (MNCWISQ)" was used for data collection. Three hypotheses were tested, using Pearson product moment correlation. The study established that there was a significant relationship between physical factors (location of immunization services/access to immunization centres/distance to immunization centres) and non-compliance with immunization schedule ($r = -.47$, $df = 298$, $p < .05$). Psychological factor (mothers' knowledge about immunization) was also found to be significantly associated with non-compliance with immunization schedule ($r = .34$, $df = 298$, $p < .05$). The study equally established that psychological factor (mothers' attitudes to immunization) had significant relationship with non-compliance with immunization schedule ($r = .26$, $df = 298$, $p < .05$). Based on the above findings, the following recommendations were made that; nurses and medical social workers should provide adequate health information to the child bearing women on types of vaccines, immunization, immunization schedule and consequences of non-compliance with immunization schedule. The government should provide adequate medical personnel and good quality vaccines in the immunization centres and ensure that immunization centres are not too far from the pregnant women and nursing mothers.

KEYWORDS: Physical and psychological factors, maternal non-compliance, immunization, immunization schedule, children 0-2 years.

INTRODUCTION

According to USAID (2003), immunity is the ability of the body to tolerate material that is indigenous to it and eliminate material that is foreign. It refers to production from microbes recognized as foreign (Abdulkarim, Ibrahim, Fawi, Adebayo, and Johnson, 2011). The immune system is composed of organs and specialized cells that protect the body by identifying harmful substances known as antigens, and by destroying them by using antibodies and other specialized substances and cells (USAID, 2003; and Abdulkarim, et al. 2011).

Chaloner, Chan-Pensky, Hilton, Hucker, Makepeace, Patel, Stretch and Moonie (1996) defined immunization as the process of using a vaccine to protect people from a disease. According to them vaccine contain either small parts of the bacteria which cause the disease or small amounts of the chemical they produce. Vaccines are administered by mouth or injection and stimulate the body to produce antibodies which will protect the person against the disease in future should they come into contact with it.

The aim of giving immunization to children is to provide primary prevention against communicable diseases or killer diseases during infancy or childhood. To this end, Nigeria operates the immunization schedule of the expanded programme of immunization which prescribes five visits in which the children will receive one dose of Bacilli Calmette Guanine (BCG), four doses of oral polio vaccine, three doses of diphtheria, pertusis, and tetanus vaccine and one dose of measles vaccine (Federal Ministry of Health, 1995). In 2004 the country included hepatitis B and yellow fever vaccine in its schedule, recommending that three doses of hepatitis B should be given at birth, at six weeks of age and at 14 weeks of age, while yellow fever vaccine should be given at nine months of age, along with measles vaccine (World Health Organization, 2005). The summary of the Nigeria's Immunization schedule is given in table 1 below.

Table 1: Nigeria's Immunization Schedule

Types of vaccine	Against what diseases	Age given	Dosage	No. of doses required	Minimum interval	How given
BCG	TUBERCULOSIS	AT BIRTH	0.11 Months 0.05ml 12.23 months 0.1ml	1 DOSE		INTRADERMAL (Left Upper Arm)
DPT	DIPHTHERIA Whooping Cough TETANUS	6 WEEKS 10 WEEKS 14 WEEKS	0.5ML PER DOSE	3 DOSES	4 WEEKS	INTRAMUSCULAR (Upper Part of Thigh)
ORAL POLIO	POLIOMYELITIS	AT BIRTH 6 WEEKS 14 WEEKS	2 TO 3 DROPS PER DOSE	4 DOSES	4 WEEKS	ORAL
MEASLES	MEASLES	9 MONTHS	0.5ml	1 DOSE	-	SUBCUTANEOUS (Left Upper Arm)
YELLOW FEVER	YELLOW FEVER	9 MONTHS	0.5ml	1 DOSE	-	SUBCUTANEOUS (Left Upper Arm)
TETANUS TOXOID FOR PREGNANT WOMEN	TETANUS	TT. At first contact or as early as possible. TT. 2 At least 4 weeks after the first. TT. 3 At least 6 months after TT. 2 or during subsequent pregnancy. TT. 4 At least one year after TT. 3 or during subsequent pregnancy. TT. 5 At least one year after TT. 4 or during subsequent pregnancy.	0.5ml PER DOSE	5 DOSES	4 WEEKS	INTRAMUSCULAR (Upper arm)
HAPETITIS B VACCINE	HAPETITIS	HBVI At birth HBV2 6 week HBV 3 14 week	0.5ml	3 DOSE		INTRAMUSCULAR (Upper Arm)
VITAMINE A		9 MONTHS 15 MONTHS	100,000iu 200,000iu	2 DOSES	6 MONTHS	ORAL

Source: BASIC (2004), Basic guide for routine immunization for service providers. Nigeria Bulletin of Epidemiology 2, 3-9.

As could be seen in Table 1, Nigeria's immunization schedule contains Tetanus Toxoid (TT), BCG (Bacilli Calmette Guanine), Hepatitis B vaccine (HBV), OPV, DPT, Measles, Cerebrospinal meningitis vaccine (CSM) for type A and C, Yellow Fever vaccine (YF) and vitamin A. According to Basic (2004), routine immunization schedule among others include

- ❖ BCG – At birth or as soon as possible after birth
- ❖ OPV – At birth and at 6, 10, and 14 weeks of age
- ❖ DPT – At 6, 10 and 14 weeks of age
- ❖ Hepatitis B – At birth, 6 and 14 weeks
- ❖ Measles – At 9 months of age
- ❖ Tetanus Toxoid – At first contact or as early as possible, and 4 weeks after, 6 months, one year and at least one year after T.T or during subsequent pregnancy.

Compliance with this schedule implies that mothers will bring their children for immunizations at the specified period or interval which will definitely help in reducing rates of infant mortality. However, non-compliance with immunization schedule may predispose the children to diseases that are preventable by vaccines, thereby promoting complications and increasing rates of infant mortality (Matsui, 2005).

Several factors can be held responsible for maternal non-compliance with immunization schedules and their consequences. One of such factors is lack of knowledge about immunization schedules. For instance, studies have shown that knowledge gaps underlie low compliance with immunization schedules (Harmanci, Gurbuz, Torun, Tumerdem and Erturk, 2003, Bond, Nolan, and Carlin, 2004). Therefore, mothers are less likely to complete immunization schedules if they are poorly informed about the need for immunization.

Education has also been found to be one of the socio-cultural characteristics predisposing an individual to utilize health care facility, including immunization programme (Opayemi, 2005). In a study conducted by Borras, Dominguez, Fuentes, Batalla, Cardenosa and Plasencia (2009), it was found that there was a relationship between greater immunization coverage and maternal educational level. High, Lean, Simon-Pierre, Nhan, Charles, Kanya, Nathan, and Danalds (2004) found that educational status of the parents is has a relationship with non-compliance with immunization schedule. They found that 77% of children whose mothers had completed secondary education or higher education had been immunized against measles when compared with 53% of children whose mothers had not completed primary school. Also they found that 48% of children whose mothers had completed secondary education or higher education were completely immunized when compared with 21% of children whose mothers had not completed primary school.

Shuaib, Kimbrough, Roofe, McGwin and Jolly (2010) in their study among residents in St Mar, Jamaica, found that participants with less than secondary school education were more likely to be non-compliant with immunization schedule, while participants who were aware of legislation against non-compliance with immunization were less likely to fail to immunize their children. They concluded that policy makers and programme managers need to use established educational and communication channels to increase awareness of child immunization especially among families with lower educational levels in the parish.

Onyiriuka (2005) found that in Benin city the default rate for the entire series of immunization was 27.6%, which was lower than the 37.2% reported in Ilorin (Musa, 2003). The explanation for this was that a greater proportion of respondents had tertiary education compared to the Ilorin study. Farag, Al-Mazrou, Al-Jefry, Al-Sheri, Baldo, and Mohammed (2005) found that there is no marked difference between immunization coverage level between rural and urban settings. They also found that the non-immunized group belongs exclusively to illiterate mothers, while children of mothers with basic education showed the highest coverage (80%). The educational level of parents showed positive impact on immunization certificate availability.

Religious belief systems also affect maternal health care utilization which may consequently lead to non-compliance with immunization schedule. For most instances, women in purdah have limited access to health care. Nath, Sinah, Awasthi, Bhushau, Kumar and Singh (2007) found that immunization and unimmunization status of children were associated with muslim religion which limit access to immunization centres. Therefore, those women who strictly hold to religious belief have a higher risk of not complying with the immunization schedule.

Some studies have also shown the effect of socio-economic factors on compliance. For instance, Okada and Wan, (2006) found that persons with low income and people living in low income areas are usually at a disadvantage in access to health care. Anah, Etuk and Udo (2006) found that mothers in the lower socio-economic groups contributed the greatest number of partially immunized and unimmunized children. A study by Mellvonnys and Barr (2007) confirmed that long distance and high cost of transportation to and from the clinic were associated with completion of immunization. Thus, the closer the infant lived to the hospital, the more likely it is to be fully immunized. Azharul (2005) found that non-completions of immunization schedule were most prevalent among members of disadvantage populations.

Pev (2007) carried out a study in Guinea on how economic factors play with intra house decision and found that to have a child immunized rests with the man, but the responsibility of actually taking the child to be immunized usually rests with the mother. In a study done by Azharul (2005), it was found that mothers who had family support had complete immunization for their children while those whose husbands and in-laws were not supportive did not have complete immunizations for their children. The study also revealed that people who lack social support have higher rates of non-adherence than people with adequate social support.

Odusanya, Alufohai, Meurice and Ahonkhai (2008) investigated the determinants of vaccination coverage in rural Nigeria. They found that mother's knowledge of immunization and vaccination at a privately funded health facility were significantly correlated with the rate of full immunization. Ayebo, Sadoh, Charles and Eregie (2009) evaluated 512 children for timelines in receiving vaccines and the completion rates of the schedule. They found that about 30% of the children presented after four weeks of age for their first immunization, 18.9 – 65% of the children were delayed in receiving various vaccines compared to the recommended ages for receiving the vaccines and only 227 (44.3%) children were fully immunized. Abdulraheem, Onajole, Jimoh and Oladipo (2011) in their study explored factors influencing incomplete vaccination among rural Nigerian Children. They found that parents' objection, disagreement or concern about immunization safety accounted for 38.8%, long distance walking 17.5% and long waiting time at the health facility 15.2% are the most common reasons for partial immunization. They also found that about 68.8% of the children were not fully immunized by one year of age, 34.4% had experienced a missed opportunity for immunization, and 36.4% were partially and incorrectly immunized.

Some physical and psychological factors have been found associated with immunization coverage and failure to complete childhood immunization. For instance, a study by Anah, Etuk and Udo (2006) revealed that physical factor such as change of residence was one of the reasons given by mothers for missing scheduled immunization.

In another study by Rafiqul, Mahfuzar, and Mosfequr (2007), it was found that physical factor such as place of delivery had highly significant effect on child immunization. They found that mothers who delivered at health institutions such as hospitals and clinics were more likely to have their children given the polio vaccine on delivery than those who delivered at home.

Similarly, Odiit and Amuge (2003) in their cross-sectional descriptive study on comparison of vaccination status of children born in health units and those born at home, found that children born in a health unit were more likely to be up to-date with their vaccination compared to those born at home. Being born at home as a physical factor was found to be a risk factor for incomplete or non-vaccination.

In Kenya, Ndiritu, Cowgill, Ismail, et al (2006) carried out a study on immunization coverage and risk factors for failure to immunize children below one year for DPT. The study revealed that immunization coverage declined with increasing distance as a physical factor from the vaccination clinics. Singh and Yadav (2001) in their study found that physical factors such as urban slums had significant impact on demand for immunization services. They found that slum dwellers in India did not demand for immunization services. They observed low utilization of health services including immunization services among the slum dwellers.

In a cohort study of childhood immunization on 760 newborns in rural Malawi, Vaahtera, Kulmala, Maleta, Cullinau, Salin and Ashron (2000) found that low immunization coverage was associated with physical factors such as living in villages with no access to mobile vaccination teams and birth at home. Sebanhat and Nadi (2006) in their study among 221 respondents investigated the reasons for non-vaccinations and the effects of

socio-demographic factors on vaccinations in a district of Istanbul, Turkey. They found that physical factor such as distance from the health centre was significantly related to the level of immunization coverage.

Ibnouf, VandenBorne, and Maarse (2007) found that children in urban and rural areas differed significantly in their reported vaccination coverage and their receipt of each vaccine. They found that in urban areas, accessibility to immunization centres is high compared to rural areas where amidst the few centres immunization is schedule based.

Psychological factors such as attitudes, beliefs, negative experiences knowledge, and hesitation have been found to be significantly associated with childhood immunization. For instance, Vannice, Shalmon, Shui, Omer et al (2011) in their study determined if giving vaccine-information materials before the 2-month vaccination visit to mothers with concerns about vaccine safety positively changed their attitudes and beliefs about vaccine safety. They found that mothers in all groups were significantly more likely to respond positively to questions and statements supporting the safety and importance of vaccines. Also, they found that mothers who received the information at earlier visits were not significantly more likely to respond positively than mothers who received the information at the 2-month vaccination visit, however, participating mothers indicated a preference for receiving vaccine information before the first vaccination visit. They concluded that the distribution of the vaccine - information pamphlet and vaccine information statements significantly improved attitudes about vaccination regardless of at what visit they were provided.

Angelillo, Ricciardi, Rossi, and Pantisano et al (1999) evaluated the knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of Italian mothers concerning the immunization of infants. They found that 57.8% of mothers were aware about all four mandatory vaccinations for infants (poliomyelitis, tetanus, diphtheria, hepatitis B). They found that this knowledge was significantly greater among mothers with a higher education level and among those who were older at the time of the child's birth. Also, they found that respondents' attitudes towards the utility of vaccinations for preventing infectious diseases were very favourable. Almost all children 94.4% were found vaccinated with all three doses of diphtheria-tetanus (DT), oral poliovirus vaccine (OPV) and hepatitis B. Furthermore, they found that birth order significantly predicted vaccination non-adherence.

In a study in immunization-related knowledge, attitudes and practices of mothers in Kinshasa, Congo, Mapatano, Kayembe, Piripiri and Nyandwe (2008) observed that awareness of immunization and its importance in protecting a child against diseases was universal, although most mothers could not tell exactly against which disease. They found that 98% of mothers had positive attitudes toward immunization. Also that found that father's involvement and mother's ability to cite signs of severity of EPI diseases were associated with the child's vaccination status in the high-coverage health zone. The mother's vaccine-related knowledge was a predictor of immunization status in the low-coverage zone.

Tagbo, Uleanga, Nwokoye, Eze, and Omobowo (2012) in their study found that maternal highest educational level was significantly associated with knowledge of reason for immunization and acceptance of immunization. Also they found that religious denomination had significant relationship with rejection of campaign for immunization. They concluded that most mother studied had good knowledge and positive perception and practice of immunization.

Nisar, Mirza, and Qadri (2010) in their study among mothers in Karachi, Pakistan, found that majority of the mothers were illiterate, belonging to low-income group and not aware about the name of diseases in EPI programme. Also, 70% of the women started routine immunization of the child and a positive attitude was reflected from both the parents toward immunization. However, they found that lack of knowledge of mothers regarding immunization leads to incomplete immunization status of their children.

Natan, Aharon, Palickshvilli and Gurman (2011) examined whether the model based on the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) succeeds in predicting mothers' intention to vaccinate their daughters against the human papilloma virus infection. They found that psychological factors such as behavioural beliefs, normative beliefs, and level of knowledge had a significant positive effect on mothers' intention to vaccinate their daughters. Also, high levels of religiosity were found to negatively affect mothers' intention to vaccinate their daughters. They concluded that the TRA combined with level of knowledge and level of religiosity succeeds in predicting mothers' behavioural intentions regarding vaccinating daughters.

Underimmunization of young children had been found to be associated with psychological factor such as negative immunization experience. For instance, a study by Stockwell, Trigoyen, Martinez and Findley (2011) assessed the association between families' negative immunization experiences within the medical home and underimmunization. They found that one-sixth 16.9% of the families reported a previous negative immunization experience, primarily related to the child's reaction, waiting time, and attitudes of medical and office staff. Parents' negative immunization experiences were associated with the absence of four components of the medical home, namely, continuity of care, family-centred care, compassionate care, and comprehensive care. In addition, they found that children in families who reported a negative immunization experience were more likely to have been underimmunized. They concluded that strategies to improve family experiences with immunization visits within the medical home, medical and ancillary staff attitudes, and reduced waiting time may lead to improved immunization delivery.

Parental hesitation has been found to be an important psychological factor for lower immunization rates. A study by Luthy, Beckstrand, and Peterson (2009) investigated the reasons for parent's hesitation in having their children immunized. They found that, of the participants who reported having concerns regarding immunizations, the child's pain/crying/anxiety as a psychological factor on mother part was the commonly occurring answer. They concluded that it is important for health care providers to suggest ways parents can cope with their child's pain/crying/anxiety when receiving immunization.

A study on attendance at National Immunization days and routine immunization involving 48 mothers and fathers in Bushenyi District, Uganda, revealed that immunization coverage was due to knowledge of immunization and attitudinal beliefs. (Nuhawa, Mulindwa, Kabwongyera and Balenzi, 2001).

Stetanoff, Mamelund, Robinson, Netherlid, et al (2010) in their study on tracking parental attitudes on vaccination across European countries found that parental attitudes on vaccinations in the childhood vaccination programmes are generally positive. Also, they found that there was a negative association between parental distrust in the MMR (measles, mumps and rubella) vaccine and corresponding MMR compliance in the five countries studied. Furthermore, they found that, the relatively high distrust and low vaccine coverage for the MMR vaccine in England is also reflected in the attitude of the parents who rank mumps, measles and rubella as less serious than other vaccine-preventable diseases.

A study on parent's attitudes and behaviours towards recommended vaccinations in Sicily, Italy revealed that parents' background characteristics sources of information and social influence were not significantly associated with parental acceptance of recommended vaccines for childhood (Conigho, Plantania, Privitera, Giammanco and Pignato, 2011). Tickner, Leman and Woodcock (2010) in their study on immunization beliefs and intention to immunize pre-school children found that parental attitudes about the protective benefits of immunizing and perceived behavioural control were strong reliable predictors of intention to immunize with MMR (measles, mump and rubella).

Determinants of a negative attitude to comply with possible future vaccination against diseases such as pneumonia, influenza, hepatitis B, TBC, smallpox and SARS were assessed by Hak, Schonbeck, Demelker, VanEssen, and Sanders in 2005. They found that 43% of the respondents had positive attitude towards all vaccination, 46% had positive attitude towards having their children vaccinated against some diseases and 11% had no intention to comply with any new vaccination. Furthermore, Hak et al (2005) found that the determinants of a fully negative attitude were a high education of the parent, absence of religion, perception of vaccine ineffectiveness, and the perception that vaccinations cause asthma, or allergies.

In a study by Gellin, Maibach and Marcuse (2000), it was found that 87% of the respondents deemed immunization an extremely important action that parents can take to keep their children well. They also found that though, the respondents' overall rating of immunization safety was high, a substantial minority held important misconceptions. For instance, 25% believed that their child's immune system become weakened as a result of too many immunizations, and 23% believed that their children get more immunizations than are good for them. They concluded that although, majority of parents understand the benefits of immunization and supports it use, many parents have important misconceptions that could erode their confidence in vaccines.

Heininger (2006) in a study on parental attitudes toward immunization, found that 22.6% of survey participants felt that immunization are administered "too early in life" and 21.0% and 12.2% thought that overload of the

child's immune system and induction of allergies respectively, would be side effects of immunization. Rogalska, Augustynowicz, Gzyl, and Stefanoff (2010) investigated parental attitudes towards childhood immunization in Poland. They found that 1.6% of the parents refused the vaccination which had been offered, 38% paid for a vaccine recommended for their child. Approximately, half of parents believed that vaccination against many diseases was harmful.

The literatures reviewed above sowed the relationships among educational, socio-economic and cultural factors, utilization of health facility, partial immunization and non-compliance with immunizational schedule. It also showed the physical and psychological variables influencing immunization coverage, or incomplete immunization for children. Therefore, the problem of this study is to investigate how physical and psychological factors influence non-compliance with immunization schedule of children 0-2 years, how they can be moderated, and how the mothers could be helped to adhere to immunization schedules.

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between physical factors (location of immunization services/access to immunization centres/distance to immunization centres) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.
2. There is no significant relationship between psychological factors (mothers' knowledge about immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.
3. There is no significant relationship between psychological factor (attitude of mothers towards immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research setting and design: The study was carried out among the nursing mothers attending the infant welfare clinics in selected hospitals and health centres in Oke-Ogun area of Oyo State. The selected Hospitals and Health Centres comprised General Hospital, Iseyin, General Hospital Okeho, Baptist Hospital, Okeho, Primary Health Centre, Okeho and Baptist Medical Centre, Shaki. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study.

Population and sample: The population used for the study consists of 600 nursing mothers attending the welfare clinics of the selected hospitals and health centres, from which 300 of them were randomly selected as sample for the study.

Instrumentation: A self-designed questionnaire tagged "Maternal Non-compliance with Immunization Schedule Questionnaire (MNCWISQ)" was used as an instrument to collect relevant information on the identified variables to test the stated hypotheses.

The questionnaire contained 50 items divided into five sections, namely, sections A, B, C, D and E. Section A contains 8 items measuring the demographic variables, section B contained 16 items measuring knowledge about immunization and immunization schedule, section C contained 6 items measuring location of immunization services, section D contained 9 items measuring attitudes of mothers toward immunization and section E contained 11 items measuring the level of non-compliance of mothers with immunization schedule. The items in sections B, C, D, and E of the instrument were structured to reflect the modified likert responses of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree with the corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively. The instrument was pilot-tested at an interval of two weeks before it was finally administered on to the respondents used for the study. The reliability co-efficient gave cronbach alpha values of 0.81 and 0.85 respectively. The instrument was also reliably validated and yielded an alpha value of 0.82.

Ethical consideration: Permission was obtained from the appropriate authorities in charge of the selected infant welfare clinics and the informed consents of participants were also gained before embarking on the study. The participants were assured of their privacy, confidentiality and anonymity, hence, they were encouraged to give honest and true responses while completing the questionnaires.

Procedure for data collection: After obtaining approval to carry out the study in the selected clinics, four research assistants was trained by the researchers to collect data from the participants. The researcher and the

research assistants approached women who have babies between 0-24 months for their participation in the study. The purpose of the study was explained to them and those that were literate were asked to complete the questionnaires within two weeks. The research assistants helped the illiterate women to complete their questionnaires by personal interview. With the assistance of the Nurses in-charge of the hospitals and health centres used for the study, the questionnaires were completed by the end of the second week to prevent hasty answers. 298 copies of the questionnaire that were properly completed were used for the final analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Analysis of respondents' characteristics

The characteristics of the mothers who participated in the study were analysed, using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts and simple percentages. Table 2 summarized the results obtained from the analysis.

Table 2 gave revealed that 26(8.7%) of the respondents were between 15-24 years, 108(36.2%) were between 25-34 years, 154 (51.7%) were between 35-44 years, and the remaining 10 (3.4%) of them were between 45 years and above. Also the table showed that majority of the respondents 130 (43.6%) had primary education, 70 (23.5%) had secondary education, 50 (16.8%) of them had post secondary education, while 48 (16.1%) had no formal education.

In term of occupational status of the respondents, the table revealed that 120 (40.3%) are unemployed or housewife, 60 (20.1%) are traders, 52 (17.4%) are teachers, 30 (10.1%) are civil servants, while 36 (12.1%) belong to other occupations. The table revealed that 76 (25.5%) belong to high socio-economic class, 100 (33.6%) come from middle socio-economic class, while the remaining 122 (40.9%) are from low socio-economic class. Furthermore, the table showed that 142 (47.7%) of the respondents are Christians while 156 (52.3%) are Muslims. In term of place of birth of children, the table revealed that 70 (23.5%) of the respondents have their babies delivered in government hospitals or maternity homes, 106 (35.6%) in their homes, 22 (7.4%) in the homes of traditional healers, 40 (13.4%) in churches, 60 (20.1%) in private clinics or hospitals.

Also the table revealed that 120 (40.3%) had adequate knowledge about BCG, Diphtheria, pertusis, poliomyelitis, hepatitis B, measles, tetanus and yellow fever vaccines and their schedules of immunization, while the remaining 178 (59.7%) lack this knowledge. Similarly, 102 (34.2%) of the respondents had positive attitudes towards immunization, while 196 (65.8%) of the respondents had negative attitudes towards immunization. Regarding access to immunization centres the table indicated that 117 (39.3%) of the respondents had easy access to immunization centres, while 181 (60.7%) of the respondents had poor access to immunization centres.

Analysis of Research Hypotheses

The three stated hypotheses in the study were tested, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between physical factor (location of immunization services/access to immunization centres/distance to immunization centres) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.

Ha₁: There is significant relationship between physical factors (location of immunization service/access to immunization centres/distance to immunization centres) and non-compliance with Immunization schedule.

The results obtained from the test are summarized in Table 3.

Table 2: Distribution showing the respondents characteristics

S/N	Variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
1.	<u>Age</u>		
	(a) 15-24years	26	8.7
	(b) 25-34 years	108	36.2
	(c) 35-44 years	154	31.7
	(d) 45 years and above	10	3.4
	Total	298	100.0
2.	<u>Education</u>		
	(a) No formal Education	48	16.1
	(b) Primary Education	130	43.6
	(c) Secondary Education	70	23.5
	(d) Postsecondary Education	50	16.8
	Total	298	100.0
3.	<u>Occupation</u>		
	(a) Unemployed/Housewife	120	40.3
	(b) Trading	60	20.1
	(c) Teaching	52	17.4
	(d) Civil Servants	30	10.1
	(e) Other occupations	36	12.1
	Total	298	100.0
4.	<u>Economic Status</u>		
	(a) High socio-economic class	76	25.5
	(b) Middle socio-economic class	100	33.6
	(c) Low socio-economic class	122	40.9
	Total	298	100.0
5.	<u>Religion</u>		
	(a) Christianity	142	47.7
	(b) Islam	156	52.3
	Total	298	100.0
S/N	Variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
6.	<u>Place of Birth of children</u>		
	(a) Government Hospitals/ Maternity Homes	70	23.5
	(b) At Homes	106	35.6
	(c) Homes of Traditional Healers	22	7.4
	(d) Churches	40	13.4
	(e) Private Hospitals/Clinics	60	20.1
	Total	298	100.0
7.	<u>Knowledge about Immunization</u>		
	(a) Has adequate knowledge	120	40.3
	(b) Lack adequate knowledge	178	59.7
	Total	298	100.0
8.	<u>Attitude towards Immunization</u>		
	(a) Positive attitude	102	34.2
	(b) Negative attitude	196	65.8
	Total	298	100.0
9.	<u>Access to Immunization Centres</u>		
	(a) Easy access	117	39.3
	(b) Poor access	181	60.7
	Total	298	100.0

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relationship between location of immunization service and non-compliance with immunization schedule

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	r-calculated	r-critical	P	Remark
Location of immunization services/Access to immunization centres/distance to immunization Services	21.8467	4.4387	298	.47	.16	.000	significant
Non-compliance with immunization schedule	59.4967	11.1351					

It is shown in Table 3 that there was significant relationship between physical factors (location of immunization services/access to immunization centres/distance to immunization centres) and non-compliance with immunization schedule. ($r = .47$, $df = 298$, $p < .05$). The result does not give support to the hypothesis. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The above result implies that physical factors (location of immunization services/access to immunization centres/distance to immunization centres) greatly influenced maternal non-compliance with immunization schedule.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between psychological factors (mothers' knowledge about immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.

Ha₂: There is significant relationship between psychological factors (mothers' knowledge about immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.

The results obtained from testing the hypothesis are summarized in table 4 below.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relationship Between mothers' knowledge about immunization and non-compliance with immunization schedule

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	r-calculated	r-critical	P	Remark
Mothers' knowledge about immunization	25.2500	2.2564	298	.34	.16	.000	Significant
Non-compliance with immunization schedule	59.4967	11.1351					

Table 4 revealed that there was significant relationship between psychological factors (mothers' knowledge about immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule ($r = .34$, $df = 298$, $p < .05$). The result does not give support to the hypothesis. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The above results indicated that psychological factors (mothers' knowledge about immunization) greatly influenced their non-compliance with immunization schedule.

Ho₃: There is significant relationship between psychological factors (attitude of mothers towards immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.

Ha₃: There is significant relationship between psychological factors (attitude of mothers towards immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule.

The results obtained from testing the hypothesis are summarized in table 5 below.

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relationship between attitude of mothers towards immunization and non compliance with immunization schedule

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	r-calculated	r-critical	P	Remark
Mothers attitude towards immunization	11.9233	2.600	298	.26	.16	.000	Significant
Non-compliance with immunization schedule	58.4967	11.1351					

Table 5 showed that there was significant relationship between psychological factors (mothers' attitude towards immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule ($r = .26$, $df = 298$, $p < .05$). The above result does not give support to the hypothesis. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The result suggests that psychological factors (attitude of mothers towards immunization) greatly influenced their non-compliance with immunization schedule.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the first hypothesis indicated the significant relationship between physical factors (location of immunization services/access distance to immunization centres) to immunization centres/ and non-compliance

with immunization schedule. The finding is consistent with the finding of McIlvennys and Barr (2007) that long distance and high cost of transportation to and from the clinic were associated with completion of immunization.

The result is supported by the finding of Azharul (2005) that non-completion of immunization schedule were most prevalent among members of the disadvantaged populations. The result is also in line with the finding of Abdulraheem et al (2001) that long distance walking is one of the common reasons for partial immunization. Furthermore, the result is supported by the finding of Ndiritu, Cowgill, Ismail et al (2006) that immunization coverage declined with increasing distance as a physical factors from the vaccination clinic.

It is imperative therefore, that immunization centres should be located very close to the nursing mothers to avoid travelling or walking long distances before getting immunization for their children.

The result of the second hypothesis revealed the significant relationship between psychological factors (mother's knowledge about immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule. The result is consistent with the findings of Harmanci et al. (2003) and Bond et al (2004) that knowledge gaps underlie low compliance with immunization schedules. The result is also in line with the findings of High et al. (2004); Shuaib et al (2010) and Farag et al (2008) that educational status of parents is associated with non-compliance with immunization schedule. Furthermore, the result corroborate the finding of Manna, Chatherge, De and Ghosh (2009), that rural mothers had low immunization knowledge. Furthermore, the result is supported by the finding of Nisar et al (2010) that lack of knowledge of mothers regarding immunization leads to incomplete immunization status of their children.

The above findings showed that low knowledge of some mothers about immunization contributed to their non-compliance with immunization schedule. It is imperative therefore, that nurses, social workers and health educators should intensify their awareness campaign on immunization of children against the killer diseases.

The result of the third hypothesis indicated significant relationship between psychological factors (mothers' attitude towards immunization) and non-compliance with immunization schedule. The result is supported the finding of Stefanoff et al (2010) that there was a negative relationship between parental distrust in the MMR (measles, mumps, rubella) vaccine and the corresponding MMR compliance. The result is also in line with finding of Tickner et al (2010) that parental attitudes about the protective benefits of immunizing and perceived behavioural control were a strong reliable predictors of intention to immunize with MMR (measles, mumps, rubella). The result is consistent with the finding of Martinez and Findley (2011) that children in families who reported a negative immunization experience were more likely to have been underimmunized.

Findings from the study revealed that the poor or negative attitudes of the women toward immunization and their failure to comply with immunization schedule are due to adverse effects of previous immunizations, waiting for long period at the clinics, incessant shortage of vaccines, believing that immunization is not needed for their children and ignorance about the importance of immunizing their children. It is imperative therefore, that the government and health care-givers should help by addressing the above issues properly.

CONCLUSION

Immunization against childhood diseases such as tuberculosis, poliomyelitis, measles, whooping cough (pertussis) diphtheria, tetanus and hepatitis B, reduce childhood morbidity and mortality (Centres for disease control and prevention, 2008). However, when mothers fail to receive adequate or full immunization for their children, many of them could suffer from vaccine preventable diseases, or suffer from impaired physical growth, cognitive development, emotional development, social skills or even die.

Findings from the present study indicated that the physical factors such as location of immunization centres, distance from immunization centres, access to the immunization centres and physical factors (knowledge about immunization and attitudes of the mothers towards immunization) greatly affected compliance with immunization schedule. Therefore, factor such as physical accessibility, transportation needs, long distance walking, travelling, religions beliefs, poor staff attitude, knowledge about vaccination, mothers' attitude toward immunization and availability of vaccines should be properly explored and moderated to improve mothers' patronage for vaccination and level of compliance with immunization schedule. Also, programmes and policy makers should take these factors into account when designing strategies to increase immunization coverage or enhancing compliance with immunization schedule.

Furthermore, proper steps should be taken by the government to change attitudes of mothers (negative or non-challant attitudes) and bad practices (mother's refusal to immunize or have immunization completed for their children due to cultural beliefs or negative assumptions) as well as improving their knowledge and awareness for better immunization.

It can be summarily concluded that the problem of non-compliance with immunization schedule might be overcome by citing immunization centres very close to the mothers, by systematic monitoring of parents' attitude towards immunization, and by increasing the level of knowledge (or awareness) of mothers about positive effect of immunization and immunization schedule.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government (Federal, State, Local) should build hospitals or health centres in places not too far from pregnant women and nursing mothers. The government should provide adequate health personnel, and vaccines in such hospitals and health centres.
2. The health care-givers (nurses, medical or health social workers) should ensure that latest and appropriate vaccines that are stored within the recommended temperature range are given to the children.
3. They should not keep the mothers waiting for too long during the immunization and should avoid behaving rudely to the mothers or being insensitive to their needs.
4. They should provide adequate health information to the child bearing women on proper compliance with immunization schedule. Immunization charts showing different types of vaccines, number of doses and the period the children could receive the immunization should be properly explained to the mothers.
5. They should embark on intensive campaigns or health talks on the killer diseases, immunizing the children against the killer diseases, nature of immunization, types of vaccines to be given, benefits of completing immunization and total compliance with immunization schedule. They should create such awareness through the media, house to house campaign or using the market places, churches, mosques or motor parks.
6. The Community/public health nurses, and medical social workers should visit homes within their domains to remind mothers of the next appointment or round of immunization. They should also check the immunization cards of mothers to ascertain that they comply with immunization regimen, as well as counselling non-compliers.
7. They should avoid hostile attitudes towards the mothers. They should have warm and friendly attitudes toward the mothers in order to encourage them to comply totally with the immunization schedule.

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